

Mn^{II} catalyzed periodate oxidation of 5-chloro, 2-methyl aniline in acetone-water medium – A kinetic and mechanistic study

R. D. Kaushik^{*a}, Purnima Sundriyal^a, Payal Rathi^a, Sushma^a and Rajendra Yadav^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Gurukul Kangri University, Harwar-249 404, Uttarakhand, India

E-mail : rduttkaushtk@yahoo.co.in

^bDepartment of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Gurukul Kangri University, Harwar-249 404, Uttarakhand, India

Manuscript received online 08 May 2014, accepted 08 May 2014

Abstract : The oxidation of 5-chloro, 2-methyl aniline (CMA) by periodate ion in presence of Mn^{II} catalyst in acetone-water medium was studied spectrophotometrically from kinetic-mechanistic point of view. The absorbance of the reaction intermediate was monitored to record the progress of reaction. Many intermediates are formed in the reaction and main product is 2-chloro, 5-methyl-1,4-benzo quinone. Reaction is first order in substrate, oxidant and catalyst each. Rate of reaction decreases with an increase in the dielectric constant of the medium. Ionic strength has no significant effect while free radical scavengers do not affect the reaction rate. The value of thermodynamic parameters are, $\Delta E = 14.43$ kJ mol⁻¹, $A = 2.69 \times 10^7$ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹; $\Delta S^\ddagger = -11.47$ J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹, $\Delta G^\ddagger = 47.02$ kJ mol⁻¹ and $\Delta H^\ddagger = 11.85$ kJ mol⁻¹. Results under pseudo-first order conditions, are in agreement with the rate law :

$$d[C]/dt = kK_3K_4K_w [Mn^{II}] [CMA]_0 [IO_4^-]_0 [H^+]/\{K_2K_w + (K_w + K_bK_2)[H^+] + K_b[H^+]^2\}$$

where kK_3K_4 is the empirical composite rate constant, K_w is ionic product of water, K_2 is acid dissociation constant of $H_4IO_6^-$ and K_b is base dissociation constant of CMA. The rate-pH profile shows a maximum at pH 6.0. In agreement with the rate law and the pH dependence, the results can be explained by, $[H^+]_{min} = (K_2K_w/K_b)^{1/2}$.

Keywords : Kinetics and mechanism, Mn^{II}, periodate, 5-chloro, 2-methylaniline, 2-chloro, 5-methyl-1,4-benzoquinone.

Introduction

Many anilines have been subjected to oxidation by periodate ion¹⁻¹¹. Also, there are few reports available on the Mn^{II} catalyzed periodate oxidation some of the substituted anilines¹²⁻¹⁷. Most of the aromatic amines are enlisted as toxic¹⁸ and there is always a need of studying their oxidation and other reactions so that newer methods can be developed for detection and treatment of these chemicals. The kinetic-mechanistic studies made on Mn^{II} catalyzed periodate oxidation of 5-chloro, 2-methyl aniline (CMA) in acetone-water medium are being presented and discussed in this communication. The studies are expected to be useful in developing methods for detection and treatment of CMA.

Results and discussion

Reaction stoichiometry :

Unreacted periodate was estimated iodimetrically in

the reaction mixture containing excess of the oxidant. The pseudo-first order behavior is observed upto an inflexion point in the graphical plot between log a and time (where a is the concentration of unreacted periodate). This inflexion corresponded to the completion of first stage of reaction for which the kinetics was studied. It was found that 1 mole of CMA consumes 2 moles of periodate for initial stage of the reaction as given below.

Another molecule of periodate may react in later stages of the reaction to give other reaction products.

Rate law :

The kinetics was studied under pseudo-first order conditions. Guggenheim's method was used for evaluation of pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} . Under these

conditions, the kinetics was defined by the rate law (2).

$$d[C]/dt = k_{\text{cat}} [\text{CMA}]_0 [\text{IO}_4^-]_0 [\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}] \quad (2)$$

where $k_{\text{obs}} = k_{\text{cat}} [\text{IO}_4^-]_0 [\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]$ and k_{cat} is the rate constant for Mn^{II} catalysed pathway. $[\text{IO}_4^-]_0$ and $[\text{CMA}]_0$ represent the initial concentration of periodate and substrate. In the absence of Mn^{II} , no significant reaction occurred. The values of k_{cat} obtained for different reactant concentrations and the first order plots are seen to be in good agreement and consistent with the rate law eq. (2) (Table 1, Fig. 1).

Effect of pH, dielectric constant, free radical scavengers and temperature :

gers and temperature :

As the reacting species are differently protonated, it was considered necessary to study the effect of pH on the reaction rate and hence, the reaction was studied in the pH range 4.5 to 7.5. k_{obs} vs pH plot indicates a maximum at pH 6.0 (Fig. 3). Since the substrate is soluble only in acetone-water binary mixture, the kinetics had been studied in 10.0% (v/v) acetone-water mixtures. Because of this, it became necessary to examine the effect of varying proportion of acetone in binary reaction mixtures on reaction rate. A decrease in dielectric constant (D) of the medium, led to a decrease in rate. Graphical

Table 1. Effect of variation of concentration of reactants, $[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]$, pH and dielectric constant on the reaction rate at 35.0 ± 0.1 °C

$10^3 [\text{NaIO}_4]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^3 [\text{CMA}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^6 \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$ (mol dm ⁻³)	Acetone % (v/v)	pH	$10^3 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)	$10^{-5} k_{\text{cat}}$ (dm ⁶ mol ⁻² s ⁻¹)
1.0	5.0	4.0	10.0	5.0	4.2	2.1
1.2	5.0	4.0	10.0	5.0	4.6	2.3
1.4	5.0	4.0	10.0	5.0	4.8	2.4
1.6	5.0	4.0	10.0	5.0	5.4	2.7
1.8	5.0	4.0	10.0	5.0	5.6	2.8
2.0	5.0	4.0	10.0	5.0	6.1	3.0
0.5	5.0	2.0	10.0	5.0	3.2	3.2
0.5	6.0	2.0	10.0	5.0	3.8	3.2
0.5	7.0	2.0	10.0	5.0	4.2	3.0
0.5	8.0	2.0	10.0	5.0	4.6	2.9
0.5	9.0	2.0	10.0	5.0	4.9	2.8
0.5	10.0	2.0	10.0	5.0	5.4	2.7

Fig. 1. Determination of order of the reaction with respect to Mn^{II} at $[\text{NaIO}_4] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm⁻³, $[\text{CMA}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³, acetone = 10.0% (v/v), Temp. = 35.0 ± 0.1 °C, pH = 5.0, $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 484$ nm.

plot between $\log_{10} k_{\text{cat}}$ and $1/D$, was found to be straight line with negative slope (Fig. 2). Further, free radical scavengers, viz. acrylamide and allyl alcohol had no effect on the reaction rate, indicating thereby, no involvement of free radicals in the reaction.

The rate constants were determined at four different temperatures (35.0 to 50.0 °C), the values of different thermodynamic parameters viz. activation energy (ΔE), entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger), Arrhenius frequency factor (A), free energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) and enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger) were found and the mean values are presented in Table 2. The value of ΔG^\ddagger was temperature dependent. A high negative value of ΔS^\ddagger is suggestive of solvent interactions and the probability that the transition state may be solvated. Small value of activation energy is

Fig. 2. Effect of dielectric constant on reaction rate at $[\text{NaIO}_4] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{CMA}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}] = 1.456 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, acetone = 10.0% (v/v), Temp. = $35.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, pH = 5.0, $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 484 \text{ nm}$.

leading to the formation of the intermediate, C_4 . Since the concentration of C_4 increases continuously with time and reaches a limiting value, its concentration can not be in steady state. Next important feature is the k_{obs} versus pH plot (Fig. 3), which indicates the presence of at least three differently reactive species of reactant (which is periodate in this system) in the pH region chosen for study²⁷. Finally, the observation that free radical scavengers have no effect on reaction rate rules out the involvement of free radicals in the oxidation mechanism. The high negative value of entropy of activation supports the involvement of solvation effects in this reaction.

While proposing a suitable mechanism for the reaction under study, the speciation of CMA and periodate should be considered. In aqueous solutions, periodate is

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters

Temp. (°C)	$10^{-5} k_{\text{cat}}$ ($\text{dm}^6 \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	ΔE (kJ mol^{-1})	$10^{-7} A$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ ($\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$)	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})
35	0.96					
40	1.06					
45	1.15	14.43	2.69	111.47	47.02	11.85
50	1.25					

characteristic of catalyzed reaction. Statistical analysis confirmed that the standard errors of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger correlate and lead to the centre of temperature range used, as given by the relation²⁶, $T_{\text{av}} = \sigma(\Delta H^\ddagger)/\sigma(\Delta S^\ddagger)$.

Proposed mechanism :

The faster colour changes in the reaction mixture relative to the separation of product on standing for long time indicates the formation of the colored intermediate on a time scale of minutes and that of the final product on a time scale of hours. The overall reaction appears to involve several steps and possibly several transient intermediates, in addition to comparatively stable one C_4 , during the oxidation of CMA into benzoquinone. Further, the kinetic order of one in periodate against the requirement of two periodate molecules for each CMA molecule in the stoichiometry [eq. (1)] requires the involvement of only one periodate in the rate determining step and second IO_4^- ion to be consumed in a fast step

Fig. 3. Effect of pH on reaction rate (rate constant – pH profile) at $[\text{NaIO}_4] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{CMA}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-6}$, acetone = 10.0% (v/v), Temp. = $35.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 484 \text{ nm}$.

transformed into the three forms in water including orthoperiodic acid²⁸ with equilibria and dissociation con-

stants^{29,30} given below :

The value of K_1 indicates that in the pH range 4.5–9.5 species H_5IO_6 shall be practically non-existent and hence only species H_4IO_6^- and $\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}$ need be considered for explaining observed pH-dependence. Based on this premise, the equilibrium or free concentration of H_4IO_6^- , $[\text{H}_4\text{IO}_6^-]$ shall be related to the total periodate concentration $[\text{IO}_4^-]_0$ by eq. (5).

$$[\text{H}_4\text{IO}_6^-] = [\text{IO}_4^-]_0 \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{([\text{H}^+] + K_2)} \quad (5)$$

In the reaction mechanism proposed later, species H_4IO_6^- has been considered reactive.

In aqueous solution, CMA, undergoes the following acid-base equilibrium with $K_b^{31} = 7.08 \times 10^{-11}$.

Since in the studied pH-range, both $\text{ClCH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{NH}_2$ and $\text{ClCH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{NH}_3^+$ exist, these species have been taken into account. From equilibrium (6), the equilibrium or free concentration of amine, $[\text{CMA}]$, is given by eq. (7).

$$[\text{CMA}] = [\text{CMA}]_0 \frac{[\text{OH}^-]}{([\text{OH}^-] + K_b)} \quad (7)$$

where $[\text{CMA}]_0$ is the total concentration of $\text{ClCH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{NH}_2$.

To explain the observed pH-dependence, it is necessary to assume CMA and H_4IO_6^- to be reactive species. On this basis to explain the observed kinetics, rate law [eq. (2)], and pH-dependence, the following mechanism is proposed. In steps (8–12), $[\text{C}_1]$, $[\text{C}_2]$, $[\text{C}_3]$ and $[\text{C}_4]$ are intermediates, out of which $[\text{C}_4]$ appears to undergo very slow reorganization/hydrolysis to yield the reaction

2-chloro, 5-methyl-1,4-benzoquinone

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product, C₅. The formation of intermediates [C₁] and [C₂] in a rapid step having low values of equilibrium constants, K₃ and K₄, is assumed in the proposed gross mechanism. The catalytic role of Mn²⁺ appears to be due to the formation of a ternary complex, [(CMA)Mn(H₄IO₆)⁺], in which manganese helps in electron transfer.

Complete rate law including the pH dependence :

The proposed mechanism (8–12) leads to the rate law (13).

$$d[C_4]/dt = kK_3K_4 [Mn^{II}] [H_4IO_6^-] [CMA] \quad (13)$$

On substituting the values of concentrations of the reactive species [CMA] and [H₄IO₆⁻] from eqs. (5) and (7) in eq. (13), and taking H₄IO₆⁻ as IO₄⁻ for simplicity²⁸, the complete rate law including [H⁺]-dependence becomes :

$$d[C]/dt = kK_3K_4[Mn^{II}]\{([CMA]_0 [OH^-]/([OH^-] + K_b))\} \{([IO_4^-]_0 [H^+]/(K_2 + [H^+]))\} \quad (14)$$

On replacing the term, [OH⁻][H⁺], by K_w in numerator, and [OH⁻] by K_w/[H⁺] in denominator, and on rearranging, the eq. (14) becomes eq. (15).

$$d[C]/dt = kK_3K_4[Mn^{II}]K_w[CMA]_0[IO_4^-]_0 [H^+]/\{K_2K_w + (K_w + K_b K_2)[H^+] + K_b[H^+]^2\} \quad (15)$$

On comparing eqs.(2) and (15), we get

$$k_{cat} = kK_3K_4K_w[H^+]/\{K_2K_w + (K_w + K_b K_2)[H^+] + K_b[H^+]^2\} \quad (16)$$

Eq. (16) on rearranging becomes eq. (17).

$$1/k_{cat} = (K_2/kK_3K_4[H^+]) + \{(K_w + K_bK_2)/kK_3K_4K_w\} + K_b[H^+]/kK_3K_4K_w \quad (17)$$

The nature of the rate law (17) shows that a plot of 1/k_{cat} versus [H⁺] or pH shall pass through a minimum²⁷. On differentiating 1/k_{cat} with respect to [H⁺] in, we get the values of d²[1/k_{cat}]/d[H⁺]². The value of second derivative is found to be positive showing the plot of 1/k_{cat} versus [H⁺] or pH to pass through a minimum. Thus, on setting d[1/k_{cat}]/d[H⁺] equal to zero for obtaining hydrogen ion concentration at which the 1/k_{cat} vs [H⁺] profile will pass through minimum, we obtain,

$$[H^+]_{min} = (K_2K_w/K_b)^{1/2} \quad (18)$$

On substituting the values of K₂, K_w and K_b, we get

$$[H^+]_{min} = 0.79 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$$

It is noteworthy that the calculated value of [H⁺]_{min} is in

good agreement with the experimental value of [H⁺]_{min} of 1.0 × 10⁻⁶ mol dm⁻³ obtained from rate-pH profile (Fig. 3). This goes in support of the proposed mechanism and rate law.

Experimental

Reagents and chemicals :

All chemicals including sodium metaperiodate, CMA, acetone, manganese sulphate monohydrate were of Aldrich/E. Merck analytical reagent/guaranteed reagent grade. These were used after redistillation/recrystallization. Thiel, Schultz and Koch buffer¹⁹ was used for maintaining the pH. Triply distilled water was used for preparation of the solutions.

Kinetic procedure :

Reaction mixture containing 1.5 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ NaIO₄, 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ CMA, 2 × 10⁻⁶ mol dm⁻³ Mn^{II} and 10.0 % (v/v) acetone, was prepared, shaken and set aside for 30 h. It developed a yellow colour initially, which finally changed in to orange colour followed by the precipitation on keeping for long time. These observations indicate the formation of more than one intermediate prior to the formation of final reaction product. The UV-Vis spectra of IO₄⁻, CMA and Mn^{II} indicated these to show no absorption in visible region. Hence, for following the kinetics the absorbance changes were recorded on Shimadzu double beam spectrophotometer (UV Pharmaspec-1700) having high precision thermostatic control, at 484 nm (at which only the comparatively stable intermediate absorbs). Absorption maxima was not found to change with change in time under experimental conditions. Guggenheim's method was used to evaluate the pseudo-first order rate constants.

Product analysis :

The reaction mixture was filtered after 30 h and the filtrate was extracted with petroleum ether (40–60 °C). The extract was evaporated at room temperature. On separation of a droplet (due to water), solid residue was left on the watch glass. This solid residue was dissolved in petroleum ether and subjected to TLC (plate thickness = 0.5 mm, stationary phase = silica gel G, eluent = petroleum ether + chloroform in the ratio 1 : 4), elution time = 25 min), to get four separated components, brown, violet, yellow and orange in colour.

The brown and violet coloured components could not

be collected in sufficient amount due to small yield. The yellow component was collected by preparatory TLC, recrystallized in ethyl alcohol and characterized as 2-chloro, 5-methyl-1,4-benzoquinone on the basis of positive test for quinone²⁰, melting point 106 °C (literature value 104–105 °C²¹), UV-Vis spectrum with λ_{max} obtained in ethanol solvent at 250, 282 and 440 nm (literature values 244, 279 and 430 nm for 1,4-benzoquinones)²², IR spectrum of compound in KBr [Bands at 1632 cm⁻¹(s) (indicating the presence of C=O on 1,4-benzoquinone pattern with the possibility that the position of this band got lowered due to +I effect of methyl group^{23,24}), 3255 cm⁻¹(s) (may be due to overtones of C=O stretch as the frequency is about twice that of C=O stretch), 2713 cm⁻¹(s) (due to isolated C–H stretching²⁵), 1514 cm⁻¹(s), 1469 cm⁻¹(s) and 1393 cm⁻¹ (may be due to C=C ring stretch), 1200 cm⁻¹(m) and 1098 cm⁻¹(m) (due to the in plane C–H bending), 761 cm⁻¹(s) (a characteristic strong band due to C–Cl stretching), 612 cm⁻¹(s)(m) and 518 cm⁻¹(m) (due to out of plane C=C bending mode)²⁵], ¹H NMR spectrum in CDCl₃ [peaks at δ = 6.991 (1H, s), 6.578 (1H, s) and 2.156 (3H, s), the latter due to three protons of methyl group attached to the ring while the former peaks due to two hydrogen attached to the ring].

References

1. R. D. Kaushik, Manila, Dharmendra Kumar and Prabha Singh, *Oxid. Commun.*, 2010, **33**, 519.
2. R. D. Kaushik, Rajdeep Malik and Ajay Kumar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2010, **87**, 317.
3. R. D. Kaushik, A. K. Chaubey and P. K. Garg, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2003, **15**, 1655.
4. R. D. Kaushik and R. Joshi, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1997, **9**, 527.
5. R. D. Kaushik, R. P. Singh and Shashi, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2003, **15**, 1485.
6. R. D. Kaushik, V. Kumar, R. K. Arya and D. Singh, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2000, **12**, 1123.
7. R. D. Kaushik, R. Joshi and D. Singh, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1998, **10**, 567.
8. R. D. Kaushik, D. Singh, R. Joshi and S. Kumar, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1998, **10**, 573.
9. V. K. Pavolva, Ya. S. Sevchenko and K. B. Yatsimirskii, *Zh. Fiz. Khim.*, 1970, **44**, 658.
10. R. D. Kaushik, R. Kumari, T. Kumar and P. Singh, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2010, **22**, 7959.
11. R. D. Kaushik, Amrita, M. Dubey and R. P. Singh, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2004, **16**, 831.
12. R. D. Kaushik, D. Kumar, Anuj Kumar and Ajay Kumar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2010, **87**, 811.
13. R. D. Kaushik, R. Malik, T. Kumar and P. Singh, *Oxid. Commun.*, 2012, **35**, 316.
14. P. Singh, T. Kumar, R. Malik and R. D. Kaushik, *J. Indian Council of Chemists*, 2011, **28**, 30.
15. R. D. Kaushik, M. Kaur, R. Malik and A. Kumar, *Int. J. Chem. Sci.*, 2010, **8**, 1379.
16. Rajneesh D. Kaushik, A. Kumar, T. Kumar and P. Singh, *React. Kinet. Mech. Cat.*, 2010, **101**, 13.
17. R. D. Kaushik, Shashi, Amrita and S. Devi, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2004, **16**, 818.
18. H. M. Pinheiro, E. Touraud and O. Thomas, *Dyes and Pigments*, 2004, **61**, 121.
19. H. T. S. Britton, "Hydrogen Ions", D. Von Nostrand Co., 1956, p. 354.
20. B. S. Furniss, A. J. Hannaford, P. W. G. Smith and A. R. Tatchell, "Vogel's Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Addison-Wesley Longman Ltd., 5th ed., 1998, p. 1221.
21. J. Buckingham (ed.), "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", Chapman and Hall, New York, 5th ed., Vol. 1, 1982, p. 1139.
22. J. P. Phillips and F. C. Nachod, "Organic Electronic Spectral Data", Vol. IV, Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1958-1959, p. 163.
23. P. S. Kalsi, "Spectroscopy of Organic Compound", 2nd ed., New Age International Ltd., New Delhi, 1996.
24. R. M. Silverstein, C. C. Bassler and T. C. Morrill, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", 5th ed., John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, 1991.
25. J. R. Dyer, "Applications of Absorption Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds", Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, 1984.
26. G. Lente, I. Fabian and A. J. Poe, *New J. Chem.*, 2005, **29**, 759.
27. K. S. Gupta and Y. K. Gupta, *J. Chem. Edu.*, 1984, **61**, 972.
28. I. Kerezsi, G. Lente and I. Fabian, *Dalton Trans.*, 2004, 342.
29. C. E. Crouthamel, H. V. Meek, D. S. Martin and C. V. Banks, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 3031.
30. C. E. Crouthamel, A. M. Hayes and D. S. Martin, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 82.
31. J. A. Dean, "Lange's Handbook of Chemistry", McGraw-Hill Book Company, New York, 13th ed., 1985, pp. 5-28.